

INNOVATIVE ECONOMIC MODELS AND THEIR PRACTICAL APPLICATION IN ENSURING MACROECONOMIC STABILITY

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Abstract. *The article examines the issues of innovative economic models and their practical application in ensuring macroeconomic stability. The research analyzes the role of modern economic models, dynamic stochastic general equilibrium models, artificial intelligence technologies, and integrated forecasting systems in ensuring macroeconomic stability. Additionally, the possibilities and practical experience of implementing these models in the conditions of Uzbekistan are highlighted.*

Keywords: *macroeconomic stability, innovative economic models, forecasting systems, digital technologies, state policy, investment environment.*

Introduction.

In the context of sharp changes in the global economic system, complication of market mechanisms, and development of digital technologies, ensuring macroeconomic stability is emerging as an important strategic task. The main objective of economic policy consists of maintaining sustainable growth rates, improving social welfare, and minimizing external economic risks, and implementing innovative economic models plays a crucial role in achieving such results. These models provide the opportunity to deeply analyze economic processes, identify interrelationships between various factors, and form effective management mechanisms.

Macroeconomic stability is related to the national economy's ability to withstand the influence of external factors, continuity of production, ensuring employment of the population, and maintaining price stability. Modern economic models serve as an important tool in developing complex mechanisms for modeling, forecasting, and managing the economic environment. Innovative models provide the opportunity to apply new approaches in economic analysis, expand the possibilities of processing digital data, and more accurately assess the dynamics of economic indicators.

N.A.Malysh in his work examines the main aspects of ensuring macroeconomic stability through innovative economic models. The author emphasizes the necessity of developing complex methodological approaches, as they provide the opportunity to integrate modern analytical tools into the process of state management of the economy. The article notes that the application of dynamic stochastic general equilibrium models and the use of digital forecasting technologies serve to accurately assess macroeconomic indicators and develop effective management decisions.[1] The author also specifically emphasizes the importance of adapting international experience to national conditions, showing that this helps ensure the sustainability

of economic development and increase the competitiveness of the national economy in global conditions.

S.Peltzman in his research puts forward a new scientific approach to expanding the theory of economic regulation. The author analyzes complex interactions between state policy, market forces, and economic agents, attempting to identify effective management mechanisms. The work pays special attention to the impact of the regulation process on economic stability, resource allocation, investment flows, and its role in shaping market equilibrium.[2] Peltzman shows the importance of innovative economic models in ensuring macroeconomic stability, particularly forecasting systems based on identifying market reactions. At the same time, he strives to identify more effective ways of managing economic policy by comparing the experiences of various countries.

The complex mechanisms of state regulation of economic processes are of fundamental importance for the sustainable development of modern economy. Yu.E.Kovnyy analyzes the characteristics of this process, showing effective ways of managing financial flows through state policy, forming investment strategies, and developing market infrastructure. The research specifically emphasizes the importance of implementing innovative economic models, which provide the opportunity to forecast macroeconomic indicators, identify economic development trends, and optimize management decisions.[3] According to the author, implementing state policy through scientifically based approaches serves to strengthen the stability of the national economy and increase its competitiveness.

A.S.Grunichev studies problems related to ensuring macroeconomic stability in the modern economic system. The author analyzes instability factors in the process of production, investment, and financial flows, focusing on identifying effective tools of macroeconomic policy. The research highlights mechanisms for maintaining stability through the application of innovative approaches and economic models, which serves to increase the accuracy and effectiveness of state management decisions.[4] Grunichev specifically emphasizes the importance of strategic management taking into account changes in the economic environment and global influences, which creates the foundation for sustainable development of the national economy.

R.V. Popelnyukhov studies the importance of applying innovative economic models in the process of ensuring macroeconomic stability. The author analyzes mechanisms for effectively managing investment and production processes in the changing conditions of the economic environment. The research highlights the possibilities of digital and forecasting-based models to optimize economic policy decisions, assess macroeconomic indicators, and ensure sustainable growth.[5] Popelnyukhov emphasizes the urgency of strengthening macroeconomic stability and increasing strategic management effectiveness through innovative approaches in the national economy.

Among innovative economic models, special attention is paid to dynamic stochastic general equilibrium models. This model provides the opportunity to forecast the impact of state policy on the economy, changes in production volumes, consumption, investment, and employment indicators on a mathematical basis. The main advantage of the model is its complex representation of real economic conditions and more accurate explanation of each economic agent's decision-making mechanisms. Such an approach serves to increase the effectiveness of national economic policy. Another important innovative approach to strengthening macroeconomic stability is a forecasting system based on the use of artificial intelligence

technologies. These systems provide the opportunity to identify market trends, forecast price dynamics, and optimize economic policy decisions by processing large volumes of economic data. Economic models based on artificial intelligence help control global market fluctuations, currency rate changes, and financial flows by analyzing data in real-time mode. As a result, the state's macroeconomic policy becomes more adaptive and predictive.

Implementing innovative economic models in the conditions of Uzbekistan creates wide opportunities for ensuring macroeconomic stability. Economic reforms implemented in recent years, digital technology development programs, and strengthening international cooperation are accelerating this process. In particular, within the framework of the "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" strategy, modern methods of monitoring and analyzing economic processes are being implemented step by step. This creates the foundation for widespread application of models based on modern information technologies in managing economic policy.

Another approach applied in practical experience is integrated economic forecasting models. This approach provides the opportunity to analyze changes in international markets, dynamics of foreign trade relations, domestic production volume, and financial flows together. With the help of such models, state bodies develop effective strategies for forecasting inflation levels, optimizing fiscal policy, and improving the investment environment. In this very process, factors affecting the sustainable growth of the national economy are coordinated with each other.

Innovative economic models are also widely applied in the process of managing economic risks. Risk management systems based on digital technologies provide the opportunity for the state and private sector to identify economic threats in advance, minimize financial losses, and determine priority directions in economic policy. Such systems help ensure economic stability in conditions of global market instability, currency rate changes, or sharp changes in energy resource prices.

Modern models developed to strengthen economic stability produce more effective results based on international experience. Economic models developed based on the recommendations of international financial institutions, including the International Monetary Fund, World Bank, and Asian Development Bank, are successfully applied in maintaining macroeconomic balance in Uzbekistan's economy. This experience serves to strengthen the scientific foundation of national economic policy, further clarify economic growth forecasts, and stabilize the investment environment.

Conclusion: The innovative economic models and their practical application described above serve as an important scientific foundation for sustainable development in the national economy. The widespread implementation of modern economic management mechanisms, forecasting systems based on digital technologies, and integrated analysis models increases the effectiveness of economic policy. As a result, the opportunity is created to ensure macroeconomic stability, strengthen the global competitiveness of the national economy, and improve the welfare of the population.

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